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*Legal Capital Rules- an Outdated Concept
for Public companies?*

A Senior Honours Dissertation submitted to the School of Law in partial fulfilment of the

LL.B. Honours degree

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24th March 2017

“I know that not everyone in the EU agrees with the idea of repealing Directives in the area of company law. However, if we want to be serious about making real progress, we cannot accept any taboos.”¹

¹ Speech on “Simplification of the business environment for companies at Public event on Better Regulation/Simplification of Company

Law with the Portuguese Ministry of Justice, Lisbon, 13 September 2007

Abstract

The Legal capital regime has been regarded as a cornerstone of the European Company Law. Its set of rules regarding both private and public companies were put in place with the primary goal of protecting creditors' interests.

However, in the recent years, there has been a significant criticism of the rules on the raising of capital, minimum capital and capital maintenance which led to reforms of the legal capital rules for private companies in many European countries. This has also sparked a debate on the feasibility of legal capital rules for public companies.

The purpose of this dissertation is to consider whether the legal capital rules for public companies are an outdated concept and highlight possible reforms in that area of law.

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Introduction

A fundamental lesson of corporate finance law is that the interests of the claimants of the cash flow of one company inevitably reach a point of conflict especially when the company needs to make a decision as to how to allocate its resources. Usually, the conflict arises between the fixed (creditors) and equity (shareholders) claimants. Their interests may clash when the company needs to make investments in new projects, pay dividends to the directors of the company or its shareholders, repurchase its shares or reduce its capital.²

In essence, the most significant conflict of interest between the shareholders and creditors of a company is based on the preference of risk when investing. Since shareholders spend someone else's money, they are tempted to take on more risky projects because they reap a big part of the returns on the investment. If they fail, the loss is borne by the creditors who have a fixed claim to the company's assets and also fixed rates of return.³ Hence, the creditors' interest in having sufficient funds in the company to repay their debts is in direct conflict with the shareholders' interest of gambling.

This conflict becomes even bigger when the company is approaching insolvency and has less and less money to cover its financial obligations. In order to regulate that conflict and prevent the shifting of risk from shareholders to creditors- the legal capital rules were created.⁴

Legal capital rules are based on nineteenth-century case law and in their basic form cover all types of companies- private and public.⁵ However, a set of more restrictive rules applying only

² Jonathan Macey and Luca Enriques, 'Creditors Versus Capital Formation: The Case Against the European Legal Capital Rules' (2001) 86 Cornell Law Review 1165, p. 1166–1168.

³ Peter O. Mülbert and Max Birke, 'Legal Capital- Is There a Case against the European Legal Capital Rules?' (2002) 3 European Business Organization Law Review 695, p.710.

⁴ Olga Petroševičienė, 'Effective protection of creditors' interests in private companies: obligatory minimum capital rules versus contractual and other *ex post* mechanisms' (2010) 3(7) Societal Studies 214, p.214.

⁵ John Armour, 'Share Capital and Creditor Protection: Efficient Rules for a Modern Company Law' (2000) 63, p.363.

to public companies was created by the Second EC Directive on Company Law.⁶ The Second Directive was adopted by all Member States of the European Union. In the UK, it was first incorporated by the Companies Act 1985⁷ and later on in the Companies Act 2006.⁸

Legal capital rules can be divided into four distinct categories: (i) raising capital; (ii) minimum capital requirements; (iii) capital maintenance; and (iv) financial assistance.

The rationale behind the rules on the raising of capital and minimum capital of companies lies in the need to ensure that at least some level of asset is provided by the shareholders when the company is formed and if the capital falls below this minimum level creditors can be remedied.⁹

Capital maintenance rules can be understood as a tool for protecting the creditors against any opportunistic behaviour of shareholders which can lead to the reduction of the company's assets and eventually insolvency.¹⁰ Financial assistance rules are a mechanism that prevents companies from giving financial assistance for the purposes of acquisition of its own shares since this can lead to a reduction of capital at the expense of the creditors.¹¹

However, in the recent years, many academicians have criticised the legal capital rules for imposing an unjustifiable burden on companies without having any significant benefit for creditors which has led to numerous reports at UK and EU level on the matter.¹² Many Member

⁶ Second Council Directive 77/91/EEC of 13 December 1976 on coordination of safeguards which, for the protection of the interests of members and others, are required by Member States of companies within the meaning of the second paragraph of Article 58 of the Treaty, in respect of the formation of public limited liability companies and the maintenance and alteration of their capital, with a view to making such safeguards equivalent 2017 (The Council of the EU), from now on to be called The Second Directive.

⁷ Companies Act 1985, Parts IV, V, VI, VII.

⁸ Companies Act 2006, Parts XVII, XVIII, XIX.

⁹ Eilis Ferran, 'Creditors' Interests and "Core" Company Law' (1999) 20 Company Lawyer 314, p317.

¹⁰ Geoffrey P Miller, 'Das Kapital: Solvency Regulation of the American Business Enterprise' [1995] Coase-Sandor Institute for Law & Economics Working Paper No 32 17, p.5

¹¹ Robert Monks, 'Modern Company Law for a Competitive Economy: The strategic framework' (2000) 8(1) Corporate Governance 16, p.86-87.

¹² Reports and proposals to be presented in Chapter 2.

States have already reformed their rules concerning private companies which has led to the question of whether there is a need for a reform in the public sector as well.

Respectively, the purpose of this paper is to analyse whether the legal capital rules provide efficient protection of creditors. These rules shall be examined given regards to the arguments used in the private company case (Chapter II) and evaluation of alternative mechanisms for protection of creditors (Chapter III). Also, a proposition for reform of relevant UK Legislation shall be given in the wake of the impending Brexit (Chapter IV).

Chapter I- The Legal Capital Regime

Before evaluating the legal capital regime and the level of protection it provides to creditors, one needs to take a closer look at what the legal capital regime is and the rationale that stands behind it. In the book *The Anatomy of Corporate Law*¹³ the authors identify a notable difference between the European Legal Capital Regime and the US rules for Creditor Protection. Namely, the difference lies in the fact that Europe has created a rule-based strategy- the Second Company Law Directive¹⁴ unlike the US where that type of rules are substituted by *ex post* mechanisms which leave discretion to adjudicators to determine whether violations have occurred.

The Second Directive has created a set of specific rules on the raising of capital, minimum capital, maintenance and financial assistance. It was adopted by the Council in 1976 and has been amended several times since.¹⁵

According to Article 1(1), the Directive covers public companies limited by shares and public companies limited by guarantee and having a share capital.

A. Capital Raising

Under Article 8 of the Directive, shares should not be issued at any price which is lower than their nominal value (par value) or their accountable par. Effectively what this means is that any introduction of a no par value share by a company would constitute a breach of the Directive.

Also, shares should not be issued at a discount.

¹³ Reinier Kraakman, *The anatomy of corporate law: A comparative and functional approach* (3rd edition, Oxford University Press 2017), p.40.

¹⁴ Second Council Directive 77/91/EEC of 13 December 1976 on coordination of safeguards which, for the protection of the interests of members and others, are required by Member States of companies within the meaning of the second paragraph of Article 58 of the Treaty, in respect of the formation of public limited liability companies and the maintenance and alteration of their capital, with a view to making such safeguards equivalent (n 6).

¹⁵ For amendments, look at Appendix I.

The notion of par value of shares represents the minimum amount for which a share can be purchased.¹⁶ A similar provision can be found in section 542 of the Companies Act 2006 where a share must each have a fixed nominal value.

The reason why the par value requirement was introduced in the first place was to have an indicator for the initial sum of money the shareholders have agreed to contribute to the company.¹⁷ This would also give the creditors confidence and security that the company is able to pay its debts off because the par value ensures that the company keeps a certain financial reserve that can be used to cover creditors' claims on winding up. Par value would also be of benefit when determining voting rights and dividends.¹⁸

Moreover, as stated by Article 9 of the Directive shares issued for a consideration must be paid up at the time of incorporation of the company at no less than 25% of their nominal value.

Another requirement of the rules on raising capital is the rule for ineligible considerations for shares- namely- the subscribed capital may be formed only out of assets capable of economic assessment (Art.7). This effectively means that “undertaking to perform work or supply” may not be included in these assets.¹⁹ These rules were created in order to ensure that the share capital reserve is accurately made up of assets.

Article 10 requires a valuation of contributions in kind to be made by independent experts who must certify the value of the consideration in order to prevent a possible dilution of company assets.²⁰

¹⁶ Kenneth K Mwenda, 'Policy Issues Underpinning the Concept of Par Value: A Comparative Legal Study' [1999] *Mountbatten Journal of Legal Studies* 80, p.80.

¹⁷ J. C BonBright, 'The Dangers of Shares Without Par Value' (1924) 24 *Columbia Law Review* 449, p.449.

¹⁸ Robert R Pennington, *Company law* (8th ed. Butterworths 2001), p.21.

¹⁹ Art.7 Second Directive.

²⁰ Jonathan Rickford, 'Reforming Capital: Report of the Interdisciplinary Group on Capital Maintenance' (2004), p. 934-936.

B. Minimum Capital

The essence of the minimum capital rule lies in the requirement that when a new business is being incorporated, a minimum specified value of assets should be contributed to the corporate asset pool by the shareholders of the company.²¹ Article 6(1) of the Second Company Law Directive stipulates that for public companies “the minimum capital shall be subscribed the amount which shall not be less than 25 000 Euros.” Some Member States have decided to set the minimum capital at a higher level, including the United Kingdom which chose the authorised minimum to be 50 000 pounds (s.763 of Companies Act 2006).

The basic idea behind the minimum capital is that it serves as creditor protection against exploitation and opportunistic behaviour of shareholders by providing a “guarantee fund” for the creditors, which can cover their claims in a case of insolvency of the company.²²

It is further assumed that the minimum capital requirement can serve as a barrier to prevent frivolous incorporation and undercapitalised companies, while also being a material basis for the company’s operation, also known as “capital adequacy”. It can protect the weakest claimants of the company- such as the involuntary creditors- those who do not have a contractual relationship with the company and thus have little or no bargaining power; employees etc.²³

²¹ John Armour, ‘Legal Capital: An Outdated Concept?’ (2006) 7(01) EBR 5, p.3.

²² Francisco S Machado, ‘Effective Creditor Protection in Private Companies: Mandatory Minimum Capital Rules or Ex Post Mechanisms?’ [2009] SSRN, p.4.

²³ Gordon Y M Chan, ‘Why Does China not Abolish the Minimum Capital Requirement for Limited Liability Companies?’ [2009] SSRN Journal, p.4-5.

C. Capital Maintenance

The core of the European Legal Capital Regime lies in the capital maintenance provisions. They can be divided into three broad categories- distributions, share repurchases and reduction of capital.

Article 15 and 16 of the Second Company Law Directive require that “no distributions be made to shareholders when on the closing date of the financial year the net assets ... are or would become lower than the amount of the subscribed capital”. The rules against distributions to shareholders were put in place in order to prevent the reduction of the company’s assets which in turn would expose it to greater risk of insolvency. Shareholders are entitled to dividends from the company, but if these dividends are funded by withdrawing assets from valuable projects this will harm the company and the creditors.²⁴

Stock repurchases, also known as share buy-backs are subject to strict regulation by EU law. Article 21 of the Directive sets several conditions which have to be met in order for a stock repurchase to be lawful. Acquisitions shall be regarded lawful if given by a general meeting (Article 21(a)) and have been fully paid-up (Article 21(c)).

Companies tend to repurchase their own stock in order to acquire a “free cash flow” which they can either distribute to shareholders or invest in projects or innovation. They can also seek to boost the stock price or prevent a takeover.²⁵ However, a public policy issue emerges when shares are not equally repurchased from all shareholders- Then a dilution of assets is created and this can potentially harm the creditors.²⁶

²⁴ Armour, ‘Share Capital and Creditor Protection: Efficient Rules for a Modern Company Law’ (n 5), p.367.

²⁵ William Lazonick, ‘The Quest for Shareholder Value: Stock Repurchases in the US Economy’ (2008) 74(4) *Louvain Economic Review* 479, p.530-532.

²⁶ Macey and Enriques (n 2), p.1180.

Another requirement of the capital maintenance rules is contained in Articles 32, 33 and 34 of the Directive- the reduction of capital provision. As Article 33 specifies: “the reserve may not be distributed to shareholders”²⁷, and “may not be used for making payments or distributions to shareholders or discharging shareholders from the obligation to make their contributions”²⁸. In the event of a reduction which is not permitted under Art 33, the creditors of the company are given the power to question its validity in court.²⁹ Also, the capital may not be reduced below the minimum capital of the company.³⁰

The rules against reduction of capital were put in place in order to prevent possible misconduct of the shareholders of the company who would try to reduce the nominal capital and thus reduce the assets that could be distributed, instead of having to comply with the strict rules on distributions.³¹

D. Financial Assistance

Article 23 of the Directive provides that: “A company may not advance funds, nor make loans, nor provide security, with a view to the acquisition of its own shares by a third party.”

Article 23(2) adds that this restriction “shall not apply to transactions concluded by banks and other financial institutions in the ordinary course of business, nor to transactions effected with a view to the acquisition of shares by or for the company’s employees.” Section 678 of the Companies Act 2006 restricts financial assistance in UK legislation.

The original reason behind the creation of this rule was to prevent the so called “asset-stripping takeovers” which operate when a syndicate buys the shares of existing shareholders with a loan

²⁷ Art.33(1) Second Directive.

²⁸ Art.33(2) Second Directive.

²⁹ Art.32(2) Second Directive.

³⁰ Art.34 Second Directive.

³¹ O. Mühlert and Birke (n 3), p.707.

provided by a bank, which is, later on, payed off by the money of the company, often without security.³²

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The Second Company Law Directive designed an intricate set of rules in order to protect the interests of creditors of public companies against exploitation of shareholders. However, these rules have been heavily criticised, mainly due to a claim that they are too complicated and costly and at the same time do not provide enough protection for the creditors.

This has resulted in several amendments of the Council Directive 77/91/EEC, a proposal for reform as suggested by numerous groups of corporate law experts. Some have even suggested that the legal capital regime should be abandoned entirely and substituted with a different approach to corporate governance.

³² Greene Committee, 'Report of the Company Law Amendment Committee' (London 1926), para 30.

Chapter 2 – The Main Criticism of the Legal Capital Regime

This chapter offers an overview of the criticism the legal capital rules have received. In order to evaluate the regime, it is useful to consider two unique aspects: the main criticism and what it is based on and the principle of Freedom of Establishment of companies and its reinforcement of the recent case law of the European Court of Justice. It is then useful to briefly consider alternative mechanisms for creditor protection.

A. Freedom of Establishment

Freedom of establishment is one of the fundamental principles of European Law. As stipulated by Art.49 to Art.54 of the Treaty of the Functioning of the European Union³³ “Companies or firms formed in accordance with the law of a Member State and having their registered office, central administration or principal place of business in the EU, shall be treated in the same way as natural persons who are nationals of Member States.”³⁴ Effectively, what this means is that an EU company must be given the possibility to move to a different EU Member State and convert into a company with an equivalent structure in the host state, without losing its legal personality.³⁵

The right to freedom of establishment has been reinforced even further by several decisions of the European Court of Justice. The groundbreaking decisions of the Court in the cases of *Centros*³⁶, *Inspire Art*³⁷ and *Überseering*³⁸ have questioned the established concept of legal capital protection, making it impossible for the Member States to subject foreign companies to

³³ Consolidated Version of the Treaty of the Functioning of the European Union 2008, TFEU

³⁴ *ibid.* Art.54.

³⁵ Marc van de Looverbosch, ‘Real seat theory v incorporation theory: the Belgian case for reform’ (2017) 28 *International Company and Commercial Law Review* 1,p.2.

³⁶ *Centros* Case C-212/97, [1999] I-1459 European Court Reports (European Court of Justice).

³⁷ *Inspire Art* [2003] I-10155 European Court Reports (European Court of Justice).

³⁸ *Überseering* C-208/00, [2002] I-9919 European Court Reports (European Court of Justice).

its domestic rules on legal capital.³⁹ The European Court of Justice went even further and declared that legal capital rules are, for the most part, unnecessary for the protection of the creditors and on the contrary restrict fundamental freedoms.⁴⁰ It also concluded that it is possible to adopt other measures which are less restrictive- such as “making it possible in law for public creditors to obtain the necessary guarantees.”⁴¹

In *Überseering* the Court specified that it is not impossible that “overriding requirements relating to the general interest, such as the protection of the interest of creditors, minority shareholders” cannot be justified by “certain circumstances and subject to certain conditions.”⁴²

These conditions were previously established in the case of *Gebhard*⁴³. There the Court created four-stage criteria that had to be satisfied: “(i) the measures must be applied in a non-discriminatory manner; (ii) be justified by imperative requirements in the general interest; (iii) be suitable for the attainment of the objective; (iv) must not be disproportionate.”⁴⁴

As noted above, the Court has already delivered its opinion that minimum capital rules do not pass the *Gebhard* test as there are other measures which are less restrictive and more suitable.

As for whether the legal rules on capital maintenance pass that test, a decision of the court is yet to be seen. But as *John Armour* has suggested- it is possible for rules on distribution and reduction of capital to be taken as disproportionate and unnecessary if the host country permits a noticeably larger amount of capital that should be maintained in the company compared to the rules on capital maintenance in the country of incorporation.⁴⁵

³⁹ Wolfgang Schön, ‘The Future of Legal Capital’ (2004) 5(3) European Business Organization Law Review 429,p.433.

⁴⁰ *Centros* (n 35), at para.38.

⁴¹ *ibid.*, at para.37.

⁴² *Überseering* (n 37), at para.92.

⁴³ *Gebhard v Consiglio dell' Ordine degli Avvocati e Procuratori di Milano* C-55/94, [1995] I-4165 European Court Reports (European Court of Justice).

⁴⁴ *ibid.* at para.39.

⁴⁵ *Armour*, ‘Legal Capital’ (n 20), p.13.

B. The Main Criticism

The above- mentioned cases illustrate the judicial response to the urge for modernisation of company law in Europe. In 1999, the Company Law Review Steering Group's *Strategic Framework*⁴⁶ set a new agenda for the UK market- a more competitive economy. It concluded that generally, the law fails to recognise that the biggest wealth is generated when business participants (such as managers, shareholders and creditors) coordinate their actions instead of being extensively regulated by rules.⁴⁷

The report suggested attaining competitiveness and efficiency and facilitating transactions between corporate parties by inducing law regulations to be substituted with contractual solutions.⁴⁸ The other guiding principle proposed was ease of use of the law achieved by "minimum complexity and maximum accessibility."⁴⁹ These principles seem to question the very existence of legal capital rules.⁵⁰

The European Commission also signalled a reorientation of its approach away from protectionism and towards competitiveness and efficiency⁵¹ in its strategic proposal-*A Plan to Move Forward*⁵², the High-Level Group Report⁵³ and the Rickford Report.⁵⁴

⁴⁶ Company Law Review Steering Group, 'Modern Company Law for a Competitive Economy: The Strategic Framework' (London 1999) <<http://collections.europarchive.org/tna/20000301011924/http://www.dti.gov.uk/cld/comlawfw/chap5.pdf>> accessed 10 January 2017; Company Law Review Steering Group (n 45)

⁴⁷ Company Law Review Steering Group (n 45), p.36.

⁴⁸ *ibid.* 16.

⁴⁹ *ibid.*

⁵⁰ Armour, 'Share Capital and Creditor Protection: Efficient Rules for a Modern Company Law' (n 5), p.357.

⁵¹ Eilis Ferran, 'The Place for Creditor Protection on the Agenda for Modernisation of Company Law in the European Union' [2005] SSRN Journal 178, p.178.

⁵² European Commission, 'Modernisation of Company Law and Enhancement Corporate Governance in the European Union: A Plan to Move Forward' (2003)

⁵³ Jaap Winter, 'Report of the High Level Group of Company Law Experts on a Modern Regulatory Framework for Company Law in Europe' (Brussels 2002).

⁵⁴ Rickford (n 19).

(i) Capital Raising

The primary concern in connection with the legal rules of capital formation is based on their cost. A very serious cost is imposed by the par value rules. Namely, when the price of the shares falls below the par value, it is illegal to sell shares at a reduced price in order to raise equity which makes funding the company extremely difficult.⁵⁵ A critical flaw of par value is that it can be used as a tool to determine profits and dividends for the shareholders based on the par value which, in many cases, is above the real nominal value of the shares and can deceive those who are inexperienced.⁵⁶

The problem with evaluating the contributions in kind and the ineligible consideration for shares comes from the fact that the prohibition against contributions done by work or services may hinder the company from paying for the quality service of its workers by issuing new shares of the company which may be an obstacle especially for start-up companies, high-tech companies and companies relying on equity finance.⁵⁷

The *Strategic Framework* concluded that they regard the company's capital to be of little importance for repaying credit and preventing insolvency of the firm and the rules on formation of capital to be of little use for investors.⁵⁸

(ii) Minimum Capital

The benefits of the minimum capital requirements have been questioned in relation to both public and private companies. For private companies, where no harmonisation at EU level is

⁵⁵ Bayless Manning and James J Hanks, *Legal capital* (University textbook series, Fourth edition, Foundation Press 2013), p.27.

⁵⁶ Kenneth Mwenda, 'Shareholders And Their Obligation To Pay-Up For Shares - a Zambian Perspective' (1999) 6(3) Murdoch University Electronic Journal of Law .

⁵⁷ Massimo Miola, 'Legal Capital and Limited Liability Companies: the European Perspective' (2005) 2(4) European Company and Financial Law Review 413, p.427.

⁵⁸ Company Law Review Steering Group (n 45), p.23-24.

required, several countries have already abolished it.⁵⁹ Great Britain never created a minimum capital requirement for its private companies and the Companies Act 2006 did not change that position.

Moreover, the European Commission made a proposal for the regulation of the European Private Company (*Societas Privata Europaea*)⁶⁰ in which it recommended the minimum capital to be 1 euro. By setting this requirement so low, the Commission indirectly advised its opinion that the rules on minimum capital imposed by the Second Directive are no longer regarded as the best source of creditor protection.⁶¹

That change of heart came with the criticism that the amount of minimum capital required is too small to offer any protection as the initial capital is going to be spent long before bankruptcy, which means that minimum capital does not reduce the chance of insolvency.⁶²

The main reason behind the criticism lies in the fact that minimum capital rules are the same for all public companies -25,000 euro, despite their legal structure and business activities. If the minimum capital were to provide real creditor protection, it would be related to the business activities and the riskiness of the company's operation.⁶³

As pointed out in the reasoning of the Court of Justice in the cases of *Centros*, *Inspire Art* and *Uberseering* voluntary creditors do negotiate their terms in advance, and minimum capital requirements are not needed for protection. It is the involuntary creditors who did not calculate

⁵⁹ In 2003 France reduced the minimum capital requirement for its private companies from 7,500 euro to 1 euro; Germany introduced a new company form with a share capital of 1 euro; in its Limited Liability Companies Act 2006 Finland decreased the minimum capital requirements to 2,500 euro; in 2009 Bulgaria reduced it to the equivalent of 1 euro; they were followed by Belgium, Sweden, Latvia, Portugal, Spain, The Netherlands, Estonia, Luxembourg and Cyprus.

⁶⁰ Proposal for a Council Regulation on the Statute for a European private company 2008 (European Commission), p.7.

⁶¹ Koen Geens and Klaus Hopt, *The European Company Law Action Plan Revised: Reassessment of the 2003 Priorities of the European Commission* (Project MUSE 2010), p.31.

⁶² Fernando D Simoes, 'Legal capital rules in Europe: is there still room for creditor protection?' (2013) 24(4) *International Company and Commercial Law Review* 166, p.167.

⁶³ Olga Petroševičienė (n 4), p.219.

the risk and thus need protection. However, the lawmakers are not capable of determining in advance the capital of the company that would be enough to cover its future liability. On the contrary, German law imposed insurance requirements on limited liability companies.⁶⁴

(iii) Capital Maintenance

The rules on limits of distribution of assets have been argued to harm creditors because as stipulated by the Second Directive- Article 15- distributions should be calculated on balance-sheet data. This in most cases may not be relevant to the real economic condition of the firm.⁶⁵

The High Group Report has concluded that the present rules on distribution have become an inadequate tool for deciding whether the company has sufficient reserves to give away to shareholders since they fail to show the ability of the company to cover its present and future debts.⁶⁶

Many have argued that the strict law on share repurchases not only does not protect creditors but also harms the shareholders of the company. Share repurchases can be extremely helpful (especially for private companies) as they provide an exit strategy to shareholders. In public companies, share buy-backs can be used to reorganise the capital of the company when it has surplus cash. They can also facilitate employee exit schemes as they make it possible for the company to buy out its shares.⁶⁷

As for Article 32's conditions on capital reductions- it has been argued that this rule was created solely for weak creditors (since the contractual creditors have already agreed on their protection on insolvency). However, as *Enriques* argues- weak creditors (such as employees, trade

⁶⁴ Schön (n 38), p.438.

⁶⁵ Macey and Enriques (n 2), p.1190.

⁶⁶ Winter (n 52), p.79.

⁶⁷ Louise Gullifer and Jennifer Payne, *Corporate finance law: Principles and policy*/ Louise Gullifer and Jennifer Payne (Hart 2011), p.134.

partners and customers) are unable to exercise the veto power the Second Directive has granted them as a tool for protection since they have no bargaining power.⁶⁸ Hence, the rule on the reduction of capital is costly and cumbersome and does not provide any real protection.

(iv) Financial Assistance

It has been argued that the financial assistance rules contained in the Second Directive are too restrictive and pose a serious threat to schemes which possess reasonable goals and which at the same time do not harm the interests of the creditors of the company.⁶⁹

Others have concluded that the regulations on financial assistance have not prevented the development of a European buy-out market⁷⁰ but at the same time have failed to protect the creditors.

C. Alternative Mechanisms

Legal capital rules are mandatory rules that were put in place in order to ensure that all creditors are protected by the law equally. However, since the regime received criticism for its costs and inefficiency, alternative tools for creditor protection were proposed.

(i) Covenants

Covenants are a contractual mechanism for creditor protection. They can be two distinct categories: negative and positive. Negative covenants include limitations, restrictions and prohibitions of certain practices of the company and the positive being obligations taken by the corporation to adhere to special requirements.⁷¹

⁶⁸ Macey and Enriques (n 2), p.1191.

⁶⁹ Mark Sterling and Mike Wright, *Management buyouts and the law* (Blackwell Law 1991), p.93.

⁷⁰ Luca Enriques, 'EC Company Law Directives and Regulations: How Trivial are They?' [2006] *University of Pennsylvania Journal of International Law* 1, p.39.

⁷¹ Stephen A Ross, Randolph W Westerfield and Jeffrey F Jaffe, *Corporate finance* (The McGraw-Hill/Irwin series in finance, insurance, and real estate, 6. ed. [internat. ed. rev. printing], McGraw-Hill/Irwin 2002), p.430-431.

The Covenants give the creditors the possibility to charge a higher interest rate if imposed to increased risk or insist on collateral or negotiate the capital maintenance practices of the company.⁷² However, if the Covenant is breached, the debt which is owed to that creditor is accelerated which can be detrimental to other unsecured creditors since the number of assets available to cover all claims is reduced.⁷³

Therefore, Covenants are a useful tool for creditor protection, especially since they are based on the particular industrial and financial characteristics of the company. However, they should be combined with other mechanisms for protection in order to ensure the protection of all types of creditors- voluntary and involuntary but at the same time do not impose costs higher than those imposed by the legal capital rules.

(ii) Piercing the Corporate Veil

Another mechanism for creditor protection is the piercing of the corporate veil. The lifting of the veil is an *ex post* mechanism that is used by the courts to pay the debts owed to the creditors in the event of inadequate operation of the funds of the company by its shareholders or failure of the company to fulfil its obligations. Debts incurred can be paid up with personal assets of the shareholders.⁷⁴

The term “piercing of the corporate veil” has the meaning of evading the general rule of corporate law of limited liability of shareholders. In the UK, the lifting of the corporate veil was introduced in the historical case of *Salomon v Salomon*⁷⁵ where the court held that shareholders are liable only to the extent they have contributed to the capital of the company.

⁷² Macey and Enriques (n 2), p.1188.

⁷³ O. Mühlert and Birke (n 3), p.724.

⁷⁴ Machado (n 21), p.28.

⁷⁵ *Salomon v Salomon* (1897) AC 22 (United Kingdom House of Lords).

However, courts are generally reluctant to pierce the veil since extreme reliance on that principle may endanger the rule itself.

(iii) Managers' liability

The managers' liability against excessive borrowing and risk taking of the company was proposed as an alternative to the legal capital rules. Imposing personal liability on managers who are protected by law by the limited liability doctrine will, in a way, shift the risk from the creditors to the managers.⁷⁶

However, this risk shifting would make the managers more reluctant to make any decisions, thus losing their human capital and incurring a social loss.⁷⁷

(iv) Mandatory insurance

Mandatory insurance for businesses which are more likely to cause liabilities and have non-adjusting creditors shield the creditors from the risk of not receiving their money since the insurance company covers the full claim while being a debtor for the company. The insurers also adjust the risk based on the performance of the enterprise which reduces the incentives of the shareholders to engage in risky transactions.⁷⁸

(v) The solvency test

An alternative method- the solvency test – was proposed by the High Level Group Report. It suggested that a company should be able to distribute its assets to shareholders only if the company remains solvent after the transaction. The report also suggested that under the current regime of legal capital rules it is possible for a solvent company not to be permitted any

⁷⁶ Frank H Easterbrook and Daniel R Fischel, *The economic structure of corporate law* ([Repr.], Harvard Univ. Press 1998), p.61.

⁷⁷ O. Mülbart and Birke (n 3), p.726.

⁷⁸ *ibid.*, p.727.

distributions as well as an insolvent company that distributes and reduces its capital. The High Level Group concluded that the solvency test might be based on “Balance Sheet test or Net Assets test” or “Liquidity test or Current Assets/ Current Liability test” with further analysis needed to develop the test.⁷⁹

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It is evident that the legal capital rules do not work perfectly. However, neither do the alternative methods for creditor protection.

Nonetheless, it is still unclear whether the best means of creditor protection is the abolition of legal capital regime altogether, a relaxation of the system or a combination of the legal capital rules with alternative mechanisms such as solvency test, additional liability or insurance.

Different jurisdictions in the European Union, the USA and Asia have created different rules in order to protect the creditors of public companies from the risky behaviour of the shareholders. They will be examined in Chapter III.

⁷⁹ Winter (n 52), p.87-88.

Chapter 3- The case of Public Companies

As has been mentioned in the previous chapter, the European legal capital regime for the protection of creditors of public companies (as well as for private ones) has been widely criticised. Many countries have already reformed their rules on private companies.

Some have argued that the legal capital rules are an outdated concept for public companies and should be fully reformed.

To evaluate the feasibility of the regime, this chapter will make a comparative analysis of alternative methods of creditor protection in other jurisdictions, it will make a comparative analysis between the need for regulation of private and public companies and will make remarks on the accounting trends in Europe.

A. Private and Public Companies

The Second Directive applies only to public companies; measures taken for private companies are regulated by the Member States and often are much more relaxed- as it is the case of Great Britain.

The need for legal capital rules is more substantial in private companies' case than in public ones. The reason is that private companies are impeded by law in entering the stock market for corporate finance which leaves them on self-financing, loans by banks or shareholders- which increases the risk of undercapitalisation and lack of finance.⁸⁰

On the other hand, a particular feature of public companies is the market. Public companies borrow money from banks or use other types of corporate finance such as equity or debt finance. Financing is a repeated operation for some companies- and it is unlikely to trick

⁸⁰ Miola (n 56), p.432.

creditors into lending again if the shareholders have taken risky transactions. Also, public companies offer shares on the stock market. They are run by professional managers that usually stay in the business area and become managers to several companies at the same time. Due to their reputation on the market for managerial positions they are unlikely to permit the opportunistic behaviour of shareholders which may harm their interests directly.⁸¹

It is then logical to conclude that the fact that private companies-that are not regulated by the Second Directive- even though it is riskier for the creditors' rights have already received a mitigation of the legal requirements may motivate the relaxation of the rules on public companies- which are already regulated by the sophisticated techniques of protection of the market.

B. Comparative Analysis

(i) Capital Formation –

China

China has a more flexible approach towards the capital formation. Article 27 of the Companies Act 2014 allows contributions to be made not only in sums of money but also “physical items, intellectual property rights and land-use rights.”

USA

The Delaware General Corporate Law does not require the shares to have a par value. Section 154 DGCL provides that the board of directors may authorise the issuance of no par value shares as long as the consideration is regarded as “capital.” Section 153 explicitly states that par value may be authorised by the board of directors or the shareholders.

⁸¹ Macey and Enriques (n 2), p.1170-1171.

The USA gives public companies the right to decide in their certificate of incorporation or in a resolution the how shares should be paid and what value should be given to them.⁸²

Germany

Germany has also relaxed its laws on capital formation. Article 5(3) of the Limited Liability Companies Act provides that shares can be issued at a nominal value (although that value should not fall below 1 euro).⁸³

The Limited Liability Act permits contributions in kind as long as a resolution is passed by the board of the directors of the company.⁸⁴

(ii) Minimum Capital

China

A drastic change of its company law happened in China in 2014⁸⁵. Article 80 of the Company Law of China 2014 abolished all minimum capital requirements for public companies and substituted it with subscribed capital. It gave the shareholders the power to determine how and when the contributions shall be paid.

USA

The Modern Business Corporation Act 1950 contained a requirement that a minimum capital of 1000 dollars should be contributed by the shareholders on the incorporation of the company. However, that requirement was abolished in 1969.⁸⁶

⁸² Delaware General Corporation Law, DGCL (State of Delaware), s.157(2).

⁸³ Limited Liability Companies Act (Gesetz betreffend die Gesellschaften mit beschränkter Haftung, GmbHG) 2016, Art.5 (2).

⁸⁴ *ibid.* Art.56(1).

⁸⁵ Company Law of the People's Republic of China 2014 (Parliament of China).

⁸⁶ Richard A Booth, 'The Chronology of the Evolution of the MBCA' (2000) 56(1) *The Business Lawyer* 63, p.64.

Germany

Germany follows strictly the Directive and requires a minimum capital for public companies of 25 000 euro as required by Article 6.

(iii) Capital Maintenance

There are two types of capital maintenance rules- those requiring a specific amount of protected capital and those providing information disclosure to investors and creditors. The first set of rules is widely used in the European Union and was incorporated in the Second Company Law Directive. The second type of rules is typical for the USA.

China

China follows the US type of capital maintenance rules- giving the creditors the power to decide the amount of distributive profits, as well as increase and decrease the company's registered capital.⁸⁷ The Company Law of China 2014 provided *ex post* mechanisms by requiring that the directors of the company be liable for any loss caused to the company during their performance of duties to compensate for the loss.⁸⁸

USA

The US has based its legal capital rules on detailed and systematic information of the company's assets in order to ensure that the financial condition of the company will not deteriorate or lose its assets without a prior approval of the creditors of the company. This eliminated the practical need of having a strict set of rules on capital protection.⁸⁹

⁸⁷ Company Law of the People's Republic of China 2014 (n 84), Article 37(6) and (7).

⁸⁸ *ibid.*, Article 149.

⁸⁹ Andreas Cahn and David C Donald, *Comparative company law: Text and cases on the laws governing corporations in Germany, the UK and the USA/ Andreas Cahn and David C. Donald* (Cambridge University Press 2010), p.220-221.

The company law of the USA comprises of the company laws of the States. Many of the States compete with each other and strive to offer the most advantageous conditions to the corporations.⁹⁰

A winner of the regulatory competition is the state of Delaware. The Delaware corporate law has made the State a leading State for incorporation of companies in the USA.⁹¹ The Delaware General Corporation Law⁹² permits distributions to be made out of capital surplus⁹³ – the assets that exceed liabilities- as defined by section 154 of the DGCL. Dividends shall be paid out of net profits off the financial year.⁹⁴

When it comes to the case of share repurchases, the Delaware Law provides that every company may repurchase its shares as long as that transaction does not harm the company’s ability to stay solvent.⁹⁵

The rules on share repurchases can be considered to have a different perspective on who needs protection. The US has emphasised the need of equity investors’ protection over that of the creditors. The legal measures on creditors’ protection “are evolving from a static security deposit paradigm towards an interactive disclosure and negotiated protection”⁹⁶

Germany

In 2008 Germany reformed its company law and added solvency restrictions on distributions.⁹⁷

As required by Section 64 of the Limited Liability Act, directors are liable for any payments

⁹⁰ Richard A Booth, ‘Capital Requirements in United States Corporation Law’ [2005] SSRN Journal,p.4.

⁹¹ Mohammed Hemraj, ‘The US corporations’ preference to incorporate in Delaware: the search for justification’ [2016] Company Lawyer 256, p.256.

⁹² Delaware General Corporation Law (n 81).

⁹³ S.1709(a)(1) DGCL.

⁹⁴ S.170(a)(2) DGCL.

⁹⁵ S.160(a) DGCL.

⁹⁶ Cahn and Donald (n 88)p.251.

⁹⁷ *ibid.*,p.225.

made to the shareholders if this rendered the company insolvent unless they can prove that they were acting with due care.

However, the solvency requirement differs from the capital maintenance rules in such a way that they are not put in place in order to preserve the assets of the company in the event of distribution to the shareholders but is intended to keep the company's capability of paying its debts.⁹⁸

In the case of share repurchases, Germany implemented the Second Directive in the *Aktiengesetz* s.33 following section 19 of the Directive very closely and required shares to be paid in full before being repurchased.⁹⁹

(iv) **Financial Assistance**

China

There is no provision in the Company Law of China 2014 that prohibits providing financial assistance to a third party with the intention of acquiring shares of the company.

USA

The US Law does not explicitly prohibit or permit financial assistance provided to third parties for the acquisition of the company's shares, but it can attack¹⁰⁰ *ex post* the measure under the sections 548 of the United States Bankruptcy Code¹⁰¹ – “Fraudulent transfers and obligations” and 544- “Trustee as lien creditor.”

⁹⁸ *ibid.*, p.225.

⁹⁹ Limited Liability Companies Act (Gesetz betreffend die Gesellschaften mit beschränkter Haftung, GmbHG) (n 82), s.33(1).

¹⁰⁰ James Sullivan, ‘United States Financial Assistance IBA Corporate and M&A Law Committee 2013’ 1, p.3.

¹⁰¹ United States Bankruptcy Code (Office of the Law Revision Counsel of the United States House of Representatives).

Germany

In Germany, the Aktiengesellschaften – AGs (which is the equivalent of the listed companies in the UK) are regulated by the Aktiengesetz (German Stock Corporation Act).¹⁰² Section 71 of the Act has strictly applied the requirement of Article 23 of the Second Directive and expressly prohibits the financial assistance and renders the transactions null and void.¹⁰³

C. Accounting Trends

Article 15(1) of the Second Directive requires that distributions shall not be made out of distributable reserves or when the net assets may fall below the subscribed capital. The companies need to prepare their annual financial statements and give regard to the requirements of the Directive.

However, on the 1st of January 2005, the European Union adopted the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in pursuit of harmonization of financial standards on international level. The IFRS adopted a paper- the IASB *Framework* in 2010 which provides the general purpose of reporting. One of the main objectives of the financial reporting is “to provide financial information that is useful to existing and potential investors, lenders and other creditors in making decisions about providing resources to the entity.” This information should be used when buying, selling, or having equity or debt in the company.¹⁰⁴

Effectively, what the new accounting trend in Europe introduced as a standard was a focus on the needs of the investors instead of a focus on the creditors’ protection. That shift of policy inclined many scholars and practitioners to think that the new accounting rules were no longer

¹⁰² German Stock Corporation Act 2013.

¹⁰³ *ibid.*, section 71(a)(1).

¹⁰⁴ International Accounting Standards Board, ‘Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting 2010’ (2010), p.9.

consistent with European legislation and in particular- the Second Company Law Directive put in force more than 30 years before that.

The High Level Group expressed its concerns that the changes in the accounting standards already impaired the capital maintenance requirements of the Second Directive. The Report the annual accounts required by the Directive have already become “an inadequate yardstick” when it comes to deciding if the company had distributive assets. It also concluded that the capital protection based on the requirements of the Second Directive had become a “delusion”.¹⁰⁵

Since the introduction of the IAS Regulation¹⁰⁶ in 2002, problems related to the difficulty of cooperation of the Directive and the accounting system has emerged. This has questioned the value of the Directive in three different aspects- whether the Directive reflects the preferences of the creditors, whether it blocks economically viable projects or imposes disproportionate costs and whether the Directive is incompatible with the accounting trends and the objectives the two sets of rules provide.¹⁰⁷

The EU went even further and in 2013 introduced the Directive 2013/34/EU¹⁰⁸ that regulated the annual financial statements provided by the public companies and replaced it with the Fourth Council Directive¹⁰⁹ and the Seventh Council Directive¹¹⁰. As required by section 9 of The Directive 2013/34/EU- the annual accounts of public companies should give a “true and

¹⁰⁵ Winter (n 52), p.79.

¹⁰⁶ Regulation (EC) No 1606/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 July 2002 on the application of international accounting standards (The European Parliament and the Council).

¹⁰⁷ Ferran, ‘The Place for Creditor Protection on the Agenda for Modernisation of Company Law in the European Union’ (n 50), p.202-203.

¹⁰⁸ Directive 2013/34/EU of the European Parliament and the Council of 26 June 2013 on the annual financial statements, consolidated financial statements and related reports of certain types of undertakings, amending Directive 2006/43/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Council Directives 78/660/EEC and 83/349/EEC (The European Parliament and the Council).

¹⁰⁹ Fourth Council Directive 78/660/EEC of 25 July 1978 based on Article 54(3)(g) of the Treaty on the annual accounts of certain types of companies (The Council of the EU).

¹¹⁰ Seventh Council Directive 83/349/EEC of 13 June 1983 based on Article 54(3)(g) of the Treaty on consolidated accounts (The Council of the EU).

fair value of the undertaking's assets and liabilities". This followed the Anglo-American accounting principle of valuating the real value of assets and be equity oriented, unlike the Continental valuation –debt-focused method that focuses on the needs of the creditors.¹¹¹

One fundamental change introduced by the IFRS is the notion of realisation- under UK Law and the Second Directive (Art 15(2)) – dividends can only be paid out of realised profits- now unrealised profit can be regarded as income and respectively be distributable under the new accounting trend.¹¹²

There is empirical evidence that shows the relationship between the legal rules (and respectively the accountancy rules implied by them) and the economic activity. The starting point of analysis is the data collected by La Porta¹¹³ in 1997. The analysis concluded that the legal rules that have Common Law origin created a much broader equity market, compared to the rules in Civil Law countries.¹¹⁴

A possible reform of the Second Directive in the direction of putting the prohibition of solvency-threatening distributions would not only bring the Directive in line with the accountancy trends the European Union has used for 12 years but would also bring the European Union in line with other economies such as the USA- which would enable the EU to benefit from the international harmonisation and competition.¹¹⁵

¹¹¹ Loukas Panetsos, 'Accounting Standards and Legal Capital in EU Law' (2016) 12(1) Utrecht Law Review 139,p.154.

¹¹² Ferran, 'The Place for Creditor Protection on the Agenda for Modernisation of Company Law in the European Union' (n 50), p.210.

¹¹³ La Porta, R. Lopez-de-Silanes, F. Wisly, R.W. 'Legal Determinants of External Finance' (1997) 3 Journal of Finance.

¹¹⁴ Ibid. p.1142.

¹¹⁵ Ferran, 'The Place for Creditor Protection on the Agenda for Modernisation of Company Law in the European Union' (n 50), p.218.

D. Insolvency Law

Legal capital rules were created in order to protect the rights of the creditors to receive their money from the company. Hence, the main goal of the creditors of a company is the solvency of that company.

However, in practice, the company may spend the money contributed by the shareholders and even incur losses, choose opportunistic transactions and transfer the risk on creditors. Hence, it can be argued that the legal capital rules, especially the rules on the formation, minimum capital and financial assistance prevent early insolvency that can happen just after the incorporation of the company but cannot guarantee that the managers will invest the money throughout the life of the company in a good investment.¹¹⁶ But they cannot be said to significantly reduce the chances of insolvency.

Moreover, once the company goes insolvent, the legal capital rules cannot provide any real protection to the creditors. The reason for that is that the essence of insolvency is the inability of the company to pay its debts as they fall due- which means that the company has already lost its capital and cannot pay its creditors.¹¹⁷

This is the reason why many have proposed that the rights of the creditors can be better protected not by company law but by contract and insolvency law. This change will require a shift from shareholders' liability to directors' liability- and will introduce the American point of view on the matter- including the "wrongful trading"- which in that situation can be defined as a situation in which the director was aware of the financial condition of the firm and

¹¹⁶ Olga Petroševičienė (n 4), p.218.

¹¹⁷ O. Mülbart and Birke (n 3), p.718.

nevertheless made distributions to the shareholders- thus maximizing the loss of the creditors.¹¹⁸

The insolvency laws in Europe¹¹⁹ and UK (Insolvency Law 1986)¹²⁰ are very strict on how assets are distributed when the company is approaching insolvency- which makes it more difficult to undermine the rights of the creditors.

However, since the Continental Law seems reluctant to adopt fully the American experience, the EU may partly adapt the US law by introducing the solvency test instead. The purpose of the solvency test being to determine if the company will have enough liquidity to cover its obligations to its creditors after the managers distribute assets to the shareholders.¹²¹

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Legal capital rules are outdated. They do not offer any real protection against risk investments, underinvestment, and possible insolvency of the company but at the same time impose costs on creditors and shareholders. Other jurisdictions such as the US and China have tackled the problem by simplifying the rules on capital formation- abolishing the par value and minimum capital. They have also facilitated transactions by allowing financial assistance to third parties, contributions in kind, share buy-backs. They have also simplified the procedure of distributions- thus facilitating possible beneficial transaction and reducing the cost that both shareholders and creditors (indirectly) have to bear. Costs -which the business players in the European Union still have to bear under the Second Directive.

¹¹⁸ Miola (n 56), p.461.

¹¹⁹ Council Regulation (EC) No 1346/2000 of 19 May 2000 on insolvency proceedings (The Council of the EU).

¹²⁰ Insolvency Law 1986 (Act of Parliament).

¹²¹ Wenjing Chen, 'Abolition of legal capital requirements under Chinese Company Law 2014 and its potential influence: a comparative study in selected countries' [2014] *The Company Lawyer* 371, p.376.

Chapter 4 – A Way forward for the UK

As we have seen, the legal capital rules on public companies are outdated. They provide some degree of creditor protection but are no longer efficient and the costs imposed on the creditors, shareholders, and markets as a whole outweigh the benefits. This chapter offers an overview of the reforms on legal capital rules the UK needs to undertake in order to achieve a more efficient and competitive market in the economic, political and legislative uncertainty the British Exit of the European Union (Brexit) will bring to Europe.

A. Equity capital

There are two basic sources of corporate finance that a company can use. Firstly, the company's managers may decide to retain the company's earnings and instead of distributing it to shareholders (as dividends or share repurchases) to invest it in future projects. This technique is called internal financing. The other funding option is to earn new funds from people who are not shareholders or managers- this is also called external financing. External financing can be achieved by selling equity shares of the company to investors or incurring debt to creditors.¹²²

Company law has a big effect on the capital structure of companies in a number of ways. The increase of share capital causes considerable procedural requirements contained in the Second Company Law Directive and reflected in the respective laws of the Member States.

UK law, mirroring the Directive, requires a prohibition of allotting shares of public companies at a discount¹²³ (Article 8 of Directive) and covering at least one-quarter of the nominal value of shares¹²⁴ as required by Article 9 of the Directive; excluding work and services as a reason for allotment of shares.¹²⁵

¹²² Cahn and Donald (n 88), p.189.

¹²³ Companies Act 2006, s.580.

¹²⁴ *ibid.*, s.586(1).

¹²⁵ *ibid.*, s.585.

There has been an extensive academic debate that argued that the traditional legal capital rules for creditor protection are primarily created in accordance with debt financing rather than equity. It has also been suggested that the strengthening of the demand for equity finance will inevitably lead to the decay of austere legal rules for capital protection at the expense of more flexible rules on laws on equity finance.¹²⁶

Moreover, the idea that company law should provide various legal instruments to those engaged in business and corporate activities in order to facilitate their affairs- especially in connection with equity finance- was proposed by the Department of Trade and Industry in their Final Report.¹²⁷

It is safe to say that the predominant financial method of companies in Europe (including the UK) is bank financing rather than venture equity capital.¹²⁸

The proof that the legal capital rules on public companies impose limitations on the market for equity finance is the limitation on distributions as imposed by the Article 15 of the Directive. These limits are typically created in legal systems which would not be likely to create incentives for investment and development of the stock market.¹²⁹

The political resistance of the United Kingdom to extend the scope of application of the Second Directive to private companies led to regulating them in a much more relaxed manner.¹³⁰ The more flexible rules on capital maintenance and capital formation (including the 1 pound minimum capital) have triggered a regulatory competition at EU level and have induced a large

¹²⁶ Klaus J Hopt and E. Wymeersch, *Capital markets and company law* (Oxford University Press 2003), p.95.

¹²⁷ DTI, 'Modern Company Law for a Competitive Economy: Final Report' (2001), p.5.

¹²⁸ R. Kraakman and others, *The Anatomy of Corporate Law: A Comparative and Functional Approach* (OUP Oxford 2009), p.87.

¹²⁹ Miola (n 56), p.468.

¹³⁰ Vanessa Edwards, *EC company law* (Oxford EC law library, Clarendon Press 1999), p.54-55.

number of private companies being incorporated under UK law after 2003 and especially after the groundbreaking decisions in *Centros* and *Inspire Art*.¹³¹

However, in the case of United Kingdom (and other Member States) that do not impose the legal capital rules on private companies, the Second Directive still imposes- even though indirectly- additional requirements on the firms that wish to raise capital on the public markets. This is due to the fact that these companies need to convert to public limited-liability companies in order to be allowed to issue assets to the public- which bears the costs of going through valuation procedure.¹³²

One of the requirements imposed by Article 7 of the Second Directive is the prohibition of issuing stock for future services. This, however, creates obvious problems for the financing of high-tech start-up companies since it does not give the companies the opportunity to attract and retain talented employees by paying them with shares of the company but requires them to pay salaries- money which can be invested in valuable projects instead. Start-up companies (especially in the sphere of high technologies) are vulnerable in the first years of their life when they need to pay for consultants, lawyers and accountants on a daily basis.¹³³

As *Kubler* pointed out- “Rules on capital operate as a restriction of the freedom to contract, as they burden all creditors with risk-reducing costs which at least some creditors would prefer to avoid in order to bargain for a higher return.”¹³⁴ Effectively, what this means is that the Second Directive imposes costs not only on shareholders but also on investors who are reluctant to invest in projects which do not bring high returns. This brings a social loss of business

¹³¹ M. Becht and Mayer, C. and Wagner, H.F. ‘Corporate Mobility Comes to Europe: The Evidence’ [2005], p.3-4.

¹³² Macey and Enriques (n 2), p.1195.

¹³³ *ibid.*, p.1195-1196.

¹³⁴ Friedrich Kubler, ‘The Rules on Capital Under the Pressure of the Securities Market’ [2000], unpublished manuscript, quoted in the “Creditors Versus Capital Formation: The Case Against the European Legal Capital Rules” by Enriques and Macey., p.1198.

transactions which could have been conducted were it not for the Directive and at the same time not providing enough protection for the creditors.

Enriques and *Macey* have argued that the strict rules on capital maintenance do not facilitate an investor in liquidating one's stake in the company on the market for the public offering which will eventually avert any potential venture capitalist or angel investors. Due to the fact that they search for higher return on their investment to reimburse for their risky investment in the initial phase of the company's life- the capital maintenance regime raises the price of equity finance.¹³⁵

A higher minimum capital (like the 25 000 euro required by the Second Directive and the 50 000 imposed by Companies Act 2006) makes the entrance of new companies more expensive which on the other hand enhances the monopoly of the leading company in the particular market.¹³⁶

In recent years, there has been an indicative change on the market of corporate finance. After a period of significant and steady growth of bank lending, having its peak in 2009, the number of bank loans and credits declined due to the big recession and the credit crunch.¹³⁷ The credit crunch is the term that stands for the reluctance of banks to provide credits below the range usually identified by the interest rate on the market and the profitability of the projects.¹³⁸ This significantly impaired the lending companies received during that period and stopped many viable projects and the development of the markets.

¹³⁵ Macey and Enriques (n 2), p.1200.

¹³⁶ Robert C Clark, *Corporate law* (Little 1986), p.353.

¹³⁷ Department for Business, Innovation and Skills, 'SME Access to External Finance: BIS Economics Paper No.16, p.14.

¹³⁸ Gert Wehinger, 'SMEs and the credit crunch: Current financing difficulties, policy measures and a review of literature' (2013) 2 OECD Journal: Financial Market Trends, p.6.

On the contrary, there has been a growth in the amount of financing companies- especially those in the UK- receive through equity financing techniques such as factoring, business angels, invoice discounting. The corporate financing based on “asset-based lending” even reached a historical peak of 4.3 billion pounds in 2016.¹³⁹

The Asset Based Finance Association even concluded that with the economic uncertainty due to the forthcoming Brexit and the fall of the sterling value, businesses could face the problem of payment delays and higher import costs, to which the equity finance could offer a real solution.¹⁴⁰

B. Going Public

Most of the Member States have much more relaxed laws on private companies which lead to a visibly higher number of private companies compared to public ones. However, this deprives many businesses of the advantages the public company offers- like raising capital on stock exchange markets, distributing the risk between many shareholders, widening the shareholder pool, expanding opportunities for acquisitions, research or pursuing new markets and providing an exit strategy.

However, it is very costly for a private company to go public. An initial public offering (IPO) of the share of the company to the public would require for the private company to adhere to the laws imposed by the Second Directive which, especially in the case of minimum capital, would make a great difference.

¹³⁹ Asset Based Finance Association <http://www.abfa.org.uk> , full statistics provided in the Appendix.

¹⁴⁰ Asset Based Finance Association, <http://www.abfa.org.uk/news/134/Finance-available-through-asset-based-lending-jumps-to-GBP43-billion-helping-UK-businesses>.

If the private company needs to have a higher initial capital in order to go public, it would have to find shareholders, managers or even creditors to invest more money than they have already done which will be extremely difficult.¹⁴¹

However, it would be a big interest of Great Britain to become an attractive country for incorporation of public companies and bring as much international investment as possible. With the upcoming Brexit, the UK will no longer be a Member State of the European Union and the rules provided in the Companies Act 2006 would no longer be required to abide by the rules and procedures established in the Second Company Law Directive.

C. Reform that needs to happen in the UK

After Brexit, the UK will no longer be among the signatures of TEU and TFEU and thus will no longer be obliged to abide by European legislation, the Second Company Law Directive included. With no EU constraints anymore, the UK legislator would be free to reform the UK Company Law, namely the Companies Act 2006 in the parts where it adopted the Directive.

Throughout the years, there have been many UK Committees which proposed reforms to the rules on creditor protection. Several reports at UK level were produced by company law experts, including the Rickford Report, the SLIM Initiative, the Strategic Framework and the Winter Group Report.

Having concluded that the legal capital rules for public companies are outdated and need to be reformed in order to achieve more efficient creditor protection, and having regarded all reports at UK and EU level, as well as evidence of other mechanisms of creditor protection used in

¹⁴¹ Robert Downs, 'Do Corporations Provide Limited Personal Liability?' (1985) 53 University of Missouri-Kansas City Law Review, p.188, cited in Macey, Enriques 2001- p.1200.

other jurisdictions, I will proceed to recommend a reform that needs to be conducted at UK level.

(i) Capital raising

When it comes to capital raising, I support the recommendation of the Winter Group, the SLIM Initiative and the Rickford Report for the abolition of the par value shares and their proposition for the elimination of the contribution in kind valuation (also contained in the Art 593 of the Companies Act 2006).

(ii) Minimum Capital

The UK currently requires a minimum capital of 50 000 pounds, unlike the 25 000 euro required by the Second Directive. The Winter Group has advised the EU on keeping the minimum capital requirement. However, I recommend the UK to diminish its requirement to at least the pound equivalent of the 25 000 euro in order to keep a competitive advantage to the jurisdictions in the European Union.

(iii) Capital Maintenance

The Winter Report proposed a change of the burden of proof from shareholders to creditors when it comes to the reduction of share capital.¹⁴² The Companies Act 2006 gives the creditors the power to object the reduction (section 646) but does not specify whose burden of proof it is. I would recommend that the Companies Act 2006 be revised so that it includes that requirement in order to facilitate the companies- that in the present situation need to prove that the creditor's position is secured in order to get a court's permission.

¹⁴² Winter (n 52), p.91.

The Winter Report and the SLIM initiative both proposed a relaxation of the rules for acquisition of own shares at EU level. The UK has already dealt with the share repurchases rules in the Financial Services and Markets Act 2000¹⁴³ by regulating- s. 118 (market abuse) and s.397 (misleading statements and practices). The idea of controlling the market manipulation by imposing criminal and civil penalties instead of restricting the share repurchases used by the UK was reinforced in 2014 on EU by the Market Abuse Directive.¹⁴⁴ This indicated that the EU will go in the direction of deregulation at the expense of pre-written rules- Article 19(1) of the Directive. However, I would recommend that the UK revise section 596 of the Companies Act 2006 and impose a restriction on share repurchases to distributive profits (unlike the rule in Art.19- 10 % of the subscribed capital).

The rules on distributions contained in the Companies Act 2006 (section 830-831) and those concerning the fiduciary duties of directors have proved to be a useful tool against insolvency of companies. I would recommend that the UK keeps its rules on directors' duties and also introduces a solvency certificate (and not a "Net Assets" test as required by the Second Directive) based on current UK insolvency law which should concentrate on the reasonable expectation of solvency held by the directors of the company as proposed by the Rickford Report.¹⁴⁵

(iv) Financial Assistance

Both the SLIM Initiative and the Winter Group have proposed a relaxation of the financial assistance rule in the Second Directive. Companies Act (sections 677 to 683) has already relaxed the rules and permits a financial assistance out of the distributive profits of the company unlike the hefty requirements contained in Article 21 and 22 of the Directive. At the same time,

¹⁴³ Financial Services and Markets Act 2000, s.118; s.397.

¹⁴⁴ Market Abuse Directive 2014 (European Parliament and the Council).

¹⁴⁵ Rickford (n 19), p.979.

it has set civil sanctions and liabilities of the administrative body as consequences of unlawful financial assistance. In that particular area of law, I do not recommend any substantial reform on UK level.

If the rules on capital formation and maintenance are to be reformed, some counter-balancing actions can be taken such as improving the quality of the financial reports provided by the companies and done in a standardised manner to facilitate investors, enhance information disclosure and the creation of an e-platform where the public can access corporate annual information.¹⁴⁶

Also, Great Britain may introduce *ex post* mechanisms for creditor protection such as the Wrongful Trading and the “Fraudulent Transfer” used in the USA.

The UK may also introduce actions on the part of creditors to sue the directors of the companies for breach of capital maintenance rules as it is in Germany- AaktG- Art 62(2) before insolvency proceedings have started.

*

The reform of the Second Company Law Directive is long overdue. However, the European Union legislator is reluctant to reform the cumbersome regime in favour of a more flexible, business- oriented set of rules in order to facilitate the companies’ transactions and at the same time preserve the creditors.

The UK has a history of setting an example to other countries- by relaxing the requirements for private companies it attracts businesses from all European Union Member States- which has led to a relaxation in many other states’ laws. Now it has a historic chance of conducting a

¹⁴⁶ Chen (n 120), p.376.

reform on the public companies rules as well which may set an example to the European Union and may trigger the long anticipated relaxation of the Second Company Law Directive.

Conclusion

The Legal Capital Regime as codified by the Second Company Law Directive is outdated. Although it does provide some protection to the voluntary and involuntary creditors, throughout the years it has proven to be costly to creditors, to shareholders and to the market as a whole. Moreover, the rules have protected the interests of the bank sector on the European financial market by hindering viable transactions and undermining the equity finance as a feasible source of corporate finance.

The onerous procedures that the Second Directive requires public companies to follow when forming and altering their capital are time- consuming and at the same time provide too little flexibility which does not allow companies to react rapidly to capital market developments.

However, the legal rules for creditor protection are crucial against opportunistic behaviour on the part of managers and shareholders, and it is not reasonable to leave the protection of the creditors' interests solely in creditors' hands especially when it comes to the involuntary creditors such as the tort victims.

Repealing the Directive, without putting anything in its place or disharmonising the legislation and leaving a free choice to the Member States as to how to regulate the public companies and their creditors' interests could lead to such a significant regulatory competition that it could eventually lead to the race to the bottom in the market of incorporation of public companies.

In the author's opinion, the future of creditor protection on EU and UK level lies in a combination of ex post mechanisms of creditor protection and mandatory rules designed by the legislators to cover the rights of involuntary creditors in a manner that is persistent with the Gebhard formula- to perform a preventive function. The mandatory rules would serve as a minimum but not an absolute manner of protection, leaving the companies with a choice based

on the individual needs, business activity and types of creditors- thus providing the flexibility needed.

A way forward, not only for the UK but Europe as well may be the solvency test- protecting the creditors by avoiding distributions of assets if capable of running the company insolvent- the idea behind the legal capital rules themselves.

The EU may also base its creditor protection on mechanisms typically used in the Civil Law jurisdictions- such as the fiduciary duties of directors as required in the UK and the “Wrongful Trading” mechanism- used in the USA. The judicial development of standards unlike the Common Law set of rules will provide the companies with the flexibility they need in order to adjust to the development of the market.

Appendix

Repealed Directive with its successive amendments

Council Directive 77/91/EEC (OJ L 26, 31.1.1977, p. 1)	
Annex I, Point III (C) of the 1979 Act of Accession (OJ L 291, 19.11.1979, p. 89)	
Annex I of the 1985 Act of Accession (OJ L 302, 15.11.1985, p. 157)	
Council Directive 92/101/EEC (OJ L 347, 28.11.1992, p. 64)	
Annex I, Point XI (A) of the 1994 Act of Accession (OJ C 241, 29.8.1994, p. 194)	
Annex II, Point 4 (A) of the 2003 Act of Accession (OJ L 236, 23.9.2003, p. 338)	
Directive 2006/68/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (OJ L 264, 25.9.2006, p. 32)	
Council Directive 2006/99/EC (OJ L 363, 20.12.2006, p. 137)	
Directive 2009/109/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (OJ L 259, 2.10.2009, p. 14)	only Article 1

http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32012L0030&from=EN#ntr4-L_2012315EN.01007401-E0004

Finance available through asset-based lending in 2016

<http://www.abfa.org.uk/news/134/Finance-available-through-asset-based-lending-jumps-to-GBP43-billion-helping-UK-businesses>

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